

PROPOSAL FOR A DIGITAL MATURITY ASSESSMENT FRAMEWORK FOR THE ADOPTION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN LOGISTICS BACK-OFFICE

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Abstract: *The implementation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in logistics back-offices represents a strategic challenge that requires a structured approach to assess organizational maturity. This article proposes a methodological framework for applying digital upgrading models to the implementation of AI in logistics back-office operations. Using a hybrid methodology that integrates four complementary models (MML 4.0, MML 5.0, DMM-OP, and SMMT), the proposal contributes to the literature by presenting a systematic approach. It identifies determinants of digital upgrading and provides practical guidelines for the gradual advancement of AI capabilities in logistics back-office activities.*

Keywords: *Methodological framework, Digital maturity, Artificial intelligence, Logistics backoffice.*

1. INTRODUCTION

The digital revolution has transformed the landscape of logistics and supply chain management. New models of efficiency, sustainability, and competitiveness have been established. This movement goes beyond simple technological adoption. It transforms the way organizations understand, execute, and evaluate their processes (GOLINSKA-DAWSON et al., 2023). The integration of advanced technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, big data, and automation has enabled the optimization of inventory management. It has also improved demand forecasting, reduced operating costs, and increased efficiency in the transportation of goods (BALLOU, 2007). In this context, the importance of specific maturity models has become evident. These should measure the degree of digitalization of companies in the implementation of AI tools in back-office logistics activities. According to Tubis et al. (2024), the assessment should consider four fundamental areas: process management, performance measurement, employee support, and technology. This allows for a comprehensive understanding of the level of organizational maturity.

The logistics back-office represents a particularly favorable environment for the implementation of AI-based solutions. This is due to the repetitive, data-driven, and rules-driven nature of many administrative and support processes (TUBIS et al., 2024). Its application in this segment can support activities such as demand planning, route optimization, inventory management, document processing, and performance analysis. However, existing maturity models focus primarily on the automation of physical operations, neglecting the significant potential of the logistics back-office.

Given this gap, the research question emerges: how can we methodologically structure a framework for assessing digital maturity that guides organizations in implementing AI in their logistics back-office? The main objective of this research is to propose a structured framework for applying digital maturity models to companies seeking to implement AI tools in their logistics back-office. To achieve this central objective, the study aims to develop a hybrid methodology, this integrates multiple complementary maturity models, creating a more robust and comprehensive approach than individual models.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

2.1 Logistics Backoffice: Characterization and Processes

The back office can be defined as the set of activities and processes that concentrate more than half of their interactions on tasks performed outside the customer's presence. Traditionally, these activities focus on reducing operating costs (SAFIZADEH et al., 2003). They are characterized by their strong reliance on information flows and employee knowledge. They differ from production processes based on physical flows (GONÇALVES et al., 2025). Their high potential for automation encompasses activities such as standardized work documentation, production data analysis, process information management, and production support. The logistics back office encompasses the administrative and operational areas that, although invisible to the customer, support the entire operation through the flow of information. This includes planning and control, inventory management, supplier management, order processing, financial control, technology and systems, and regulatory compliance.

They essentially depend on information flows, employee expertise, and detailed analyses that directly support decision-making. Although essential for operational functioning, they face recurring challenges that compromise efficiency and accuracy.

2.2 Applications for AI Tools in Back-Office Logistics

AI in logistics is applied in several areas: route optimization, demand forecasting, warehouse automation, and risk management. In the back-office sphere, various tools and software solutions optimize routine activities such as document management, scheduling, inventory control, and task distribution (GARTNER, 2021). This revolutionizes workflows and increases operational efficiency.

Automating financial tasks, such as data entry and invoice processing, reduces errors and increases operational efficiency (IBM, 2021). Virtual assistants such as ChatGPT and IBM Watson Assistant demonstrate effectiveness in customer service, responding to emails, scheduling appointments, and performing support functions. Recognizing this diversity, studies highlight the importance of AI tools in optimizing administrative processes in office environments.

Axmann et al. (2025) revealed, in a cross-national study on the use of automation and AI software in logistics offices in Brazil, Croatia, Germany, and Serbia, a significant disparity. They observed extensive use of enterprise automation platforms, but low adoption of specialized AI software. The study found that only 11% of respondents use AI tools frequently, while 44% do not use them at all.

Complementing this perspective, Dolfini and Silva (2025) identified practical solutions such as Google Workspace, Microsoft 365, ChatGPT, Watson Assistant, Trello, Asana, and Forecastly. These demonstrate the ability to automate repetitive tasks with productivity gains of up to 30%. However, they also identify critical challenges, including high implementation costs, the need for professional training, and integration with legacy systems.

2.3 Digital Maturity Models

Maturity represents a state of completeness and readiness that reflects growth and excellence (FACCHINI et al., 2020). In this context, technological readiness refers to the degree of a technology's readiness for application (ELLEFSEN et al., 2019).

An organization's digital maturity refers to its level of preparedness and capacity to strategically adopt, integrate, and exploit digital technologies. This generates value in its processes, products, and business models (Barry, Assoul & Souissi, 2022). This assessment is an essential step before any digital transformation initiative. It allows companies to understand their current level of digitalization, identify strengths and weaknesses, and align their strategy more effectively.

The Digital Internet Maturity Model (DIMM), proposed by Fayon and Tartar (2019), can be applied to any type of organization. The authors evaluated the models in terms of dimensions and subdimensions, central concepts of the Onto Digital Model (Zaoui & Souissi, 2018). The dimensions correspond to broad areas of analysis, such as Digital Strategy, Governance, Organizational Culture, Technology, Processes, Data, Customer Experience, Partnerships, and Security. The subdimensions detail specific aspects of each area. For example, within the "Processes" dimension, subdimensions might include automation, interdepartmental integration, and adaptability. Within "Organizational Culture," they might encompass digital mindset alignment and workforce training.

The Digital Maturity Model Organizational and Process Level (DMM-OP), presented in Tubis et al. (2024), assesses digital maturity at two levels: organizational (strategy, corporate culture, and data management) and process (operational processes, employees, and technological infrastructure). The model uses a scale ranging from 0 to

5, with 0 representing a complete absence of digital support and 5 corresponding to the adoption of advanced technologies and best organizational practices.

Given the lack of a specific model for assessing digital maturity in the implementation of AI tools in the logistics back office, Section 4 presents the proposed framework to address this gap.

3. METHOD

The development of this article was based on a systematic literature review. It followed the guidelines of the PRISMA method (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses). The search was conducted in Web of Science, Scopus, IEEE Xplore, Google Scholar, and Periódico Capes. These were selected for their breadth and indexing quality. The search strings were structured around three axes: digital maturity model, logistics back-office, and artificial intelligence.

Four representative models were identified: MML 4.0 (Facchini et al., 2020), MML 5.0 (Machado & Rodriguez, 2025), DMM-OP (Tubis, 2023), and SMMT (Sonntag et al., 2024). The methodological integration of these models, through a structured process, harmonizes different theoretical perspectives. This creates a hybrid approach for assessing digital maturity in AI implementation in the logistics back-office.

4. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

The proposal integrates four digital maturity models with the aim of conducting a comparative and intersectional analysis between them. The structural overlap provides a multidimensional assessment of digital readiness for the adoption of AI in back-office logistics operations. The intersection capturing technological, organizational, and human aspects of digital transformation.

4.1 Selection of Maturity Models

Given the lack of a specific model for back-office logistics, four complementary models were selected to form a multidimensional framework. Facchini et al. (2020) MML 4.0 measures the degree of digitalization and technological integration of logistics processes in the Industry 4.0 era. Machado and Rodriguez's (2025) MML 5.0 assesses organizational readiness for the transition from Logistics 4.0 to 5.0, focusing on human-machine collaborative integration. Tubis's (2023) DMM-OP provides a diagnostic perspective focused on the organizational and process levels. Sonntag et al. (2024) SMMT assesses AI implementation capabilities in manufacturing contexts, offering an advanced view of industrial AI readiness. The integration of these models, with their individual limitations, creates a robust framework adapted to back-office logistics.

4.2 Framework Application Phases

The proposed framework is a structured process consisting of five phases. It begins with (1) preparation, establishing objectives and aligning stakeholder expectations. Next comes (2) configuration, adapting tools to the organizational context. Next comes (3) data collection, integrating the four models through surveys, interviews, and document analysis. Then comes (4) gap analysis, identifying discrepancies between current and desired levels. Finally, (5) roadmapping and refinement, prioritizing initiatives with continuous review. This iterative process ensures ongoing relevance, aligning AI maturity with organizational evolution.

The framework offers five main advantages: (1) it eliminates conceptual fragmentation by uniting technological, organizational, and human perspectives; (2) it offers greater detail by using different analysis methods, reducing potential biases; (3) it provides contextual flexibility while maintaining methodological consistency; (4) it ensures constant monitoring of digital maturity as an evolving process; and (5) fills a gap in the literature by focusing specifically on back-office logistics, where the potential for automation via AI is particularly high.

4.3 Models Application Modes

The framework's application follows a sequential and complementary strategy that maximizes the benefits of each model. In the third stage, the models are applied. MML 4.0 uses a structured questionnaire with 15 items on a Likert scale, administered through in-person interviews with logistics process managers. This stage establishes the baseline digital maturity of the processes, classifying the organization into one of five levels (from "Initial" to "Optimized").

The second model applied is MML 5.0, using a digital questionnaire complemented by on-site visits. This allows for a qualitative assessment of human-machine integration and sustainable practices. The data is processed using the DEMATEL method to identify cause-and-effect relationships between dimensions (Technology, People, Processes, and Culture), revealing critical drivers of digital transformation.

The third model applied is the DMM-OP, with its comprehensive 105-item questionnaire preceded by preparatory meetings for terminology alignment. This phase deepens the organizational analysis, assessing digital strategy, data management, organizational culture, and technological support on a scale of 0 to 5. This provides the most detailed diagnosis of organizational readiness.

Finally, the fourth model applied the SMMT through 29 questions distributed across five dimensions (AI Strategy, Data, Technology, People, and Organization), using paired comparison techniques to weight the criteria. This specifically assesses AI implementation capabilities, including computing infrastructure, data quality, technical competencies, and algorithmic governance.

The results are integrated through a convergence matrix that identifies: (a) strengths, the dimensions well-evaluated across all models; (b) critical gaps, the areas of low maturity identified by multiple models; (c) discrepancies between models, the divergences that

indicate the need for further research; and (d) leverage opportunities, the existing capabilities that can accelerate AI adoption. This cross-analysis allows prioritizing investments based on convergent evidence, increasing the effectiveness of digital transformation initiatives. The flowchart presented in Figure 1 represents the structured, cyclical five-phase process that integrates four complementary digital maturity models to systematically assess organizational readiness for implementing Artificial Intelligence in the logistics back office.

Figure 1. Digital Maturity Assessment Framework for AI Implementation in Logistics Back-Office
Authors, (2025)

5. DISCUSSIONS

The synthesized evidence highlights key strategies for overcoming barriers to AI adoption in back-office logistics operations. Dolfini and Silva (2025) identify high implementation costs, workforce upskilling needs, and legacy system integration as critical challenges. They emphasize that the convergence of technology, people, and processes is essential for the success of digital transformation.

Addressing these barriers requires gradual implementation strategies. These strategies spread investments over time and enable progressive organizational learning. Furthermore, Axmann et al. (2025) report low adoption rates, with 44% of professionals not using AI tools. This highlights the need for structured change management approaches. Targeted awareness and training initiatives, supported by pilot projects that

demonstrate tangible benefits, can accelerate acceptance and foster broader organizational adoption.

The integrated application of the four models reveals critical interdependencies often overlooked in one-dimensional assessments. The cross-analysis between MML 5.0 and SMMT highlights that organizations may possess advanced technological infrastructure but lack a culture of human-machine collaboration. This results in underutilization of installed capabilities. Likewise, digitalized processes without adequate data governance produce suboptimal results in logistics optimization.

These findings reinforce the central argument: digital maturity in the logistics back-office cannot be adequately captured by isolated models. It requires a hybrid approach that simultaneously considers technological, organizational, procedural, and human dimensions. The framework operationalizes this holistic vision through a rigorous methodology. This preserves individual strengths while mitigating limitations through structural complementarity.

The proposed framework advances academic knowledge by integrating four complementary maturity models into a hybrid framework adapted to the logistics back-office context. This approach addresses significant gaps in the digital maturity assessment literature and harmonizes the technological, organizational, and human dimensions into a coherent and operationally applicable model. By synthesizing determinants identified by Sonntag et al. (2024), Facchini et al. (2020), and Tubis et al. (2024), the framework provides a robust conceptual foundation for future research. Additionally, it supports the development of strategic roadmaps that first strengthen data management and digital process capabilities. This empowers organizations to maximize the impact and sustainability of AI driven transformation.

6. FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

Implementing AI in the logistics back office represents a complex challenge that requires a structured and multidimensional approach. Given the lack of a specific model, this study proposed a structured framework using a hybrid methodology that integrates four complementary maturity models. This offers a more robust approach than isolated models and enables a precise diagnosis to support digital transformation. Six main integrated maturity factors are identified: Culture and Competencies, Strategy, Data, Organization and Processes, and Technology, which provide a solid foundation for guiding investments in the implementation of AI tools.

For future research, empirical validation through practical applications, longitudinal studies, and adaptation to different industrial contexts is recommended. The continuous evolution of the framework must keep pace with technological developments and competitive shifts to ensure its continued relevance.

Acknowledgement: The authors express gratitude for the National Council for Scientific and Technological Development (CNPq), in Brazil for supporting this research in the form of a scholarship for one of the authors.

Declaration: The authors declare that they have not used any type of generative artificial intelligence for the writing of this paper. The authors are fully responsible for the accuracy and integrity of their work.

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